

**USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORY WORKS IN THE EDUCATIONAL
PROCESS AND THEIR ADVANTAGES**

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Abstract : this in the article information and communication technology education to the process application introduction , virtual laboratories and they are medical and biological physics science about topics in transition go away the importance of virtual laboratories conclusion , education process organize in reaching place about thought native

Key words : information-communication technology , education resources , visualization , modeling , interactivity , virtual laboratory , integration to do

**ISPOLZOVANIE VIRTUALNYX LABORATORNIX RABOT V
UCHEBNOM PROSESSE I IX PREIMUCHESTVA**

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Annotation: v dannoy state rassmatrivaetsya primenie informatsionno-kommunikatsionnykh tekhnologiy v uchebnom protsesse, vajnost virtual procedural laboratory va ix ispolzovanie pri prohojdenii tem, svyazannykh s meditsinskoy va biologicheskoy rolimu organicheskoe fizika, a. process.

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Abstract: this article discusses the implementation of information and communication technologies in the educational process, the importance of using virtual laboratories and their use in passing biophysics topics, the advantages of virtual laboratories, their role in the organization of the educational process.

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INTRODUCTION.

Current in time never one modern man own his life without a computer imagination do it it didn't happen . We are information and communication

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technologies (ICT) rapidly that is developing witness we will be This is education to the process big effect is showing . the main thing this technologies of students knowledge and the eye to develop help gives so study to the process right integration to do and current is to reach So study to the process information and communication technology current received with multimedia study from manuals national lecture , perhaps laboratory a virtual laboratory in training work in the form of send by being left Biophysics in science learned laboratory works national useful , maybe very interesting But all experiences are also real life in mode union about possible it's not or need not like that about visualization and the results get for virtual labs Uzbek right about electron are resources . Visualization different of events events the number and deeper to something help gives Uzbek efficient teaching methods is one . Visualization and modeling especially only static image with about difficult has been dynamic , changing objects and events in learning is useful . But one to the question sure answer order right comes : where one good , real is the object or on the screen the model when ? Laboratory their work take go each how technology his own after and material has , him transfer for known conditions necessary

MAIN PART.

today to the day come interactive , multimedia- rich education resources in the enterprise modern education process more efficient to be was determined . to these requirements Uzbek good education resources and virtual systems answer . Like this electron to resources example as computer education real world environment of objects personal affairs imitation do it person and to students medical and biological physics , like scientific and natural sciences according to new knowledge and your eyes to take over help create virtual laboratories to bring can

What is "virtual laboratory " ? VV Trukhin to the definition According to , the virtual laboratory is real installation with straight away contact do or they are there is when not experiences union about possibility giver correction - hardware complex [2]. First of all , remote access to learn have has been laboratory issue with work take will go , this while real laboratory , adjustment manage and received data digitization for as supply and depends on the hardware contact their work own about takes In this all processes computer by is modeled .

Virtual laboratory in education record necessary belongs to of course real from laboratories go away opportunity there is that it is not or laboratory work in transfer and technique about in providing coming coming day because of before it

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has been . Virtual laboratory practicum real to the experience full alternate form does not recognize [5]. Current in time modern computer technologies special in real conditions without equipment differentiate difficult has been processes dynamic so to see and time by . danger schedule time to " zoom ". person is important . For example , a laboratory at work short time inside happened to be process slowed down beam time or very long time continue man process (a how many year for happened to be cases) acceleration can And this processing thin to do realize reach and to the process deeper come in to go by in [3].

Modern student past century from a student education in the process and all in the fields information technologies wide to you take with with separately stands Modern students on the computer free work takes , computer models with familiar, different in programs work to the eye have and modern computer technologies and audio-video equipment organized present done from himself about Computer to the models property in seminars student to him near has been a new virtual world with to communicate enters (virtual world with computer games through already familiar was), as a result demand to science has been aspiration will increase , education place then Knowledge get quality about level improves strong addition motivation event

Students medical and biological physics from science laboratory works for experiences transfer and this about and they are send to the eye have will be Received experimental from the data independent results release and that's it with theoretical materials deeper and complete to master learning possible will be Virtual laboratories record in front of one is being studied processes each by visualization to do desire , profit of means one while to the student report events Uzbek complete perception reach and about for preparation to see questions is to give [1].

Virtual laboratories exhibitionism , interactivity note , separately , of students knowledge and creative activity about help .they are surroundings in the world objects and processes modeling , real laboratory from the equipment send by in [4]. Har a virtual laboratory is working theoretical at student data with get to know , experience place time possible have will be , tasks place tools the issue , the assignments solves) and done affairs take into account results product .

Students , time laboratory their work to the notebook writing take , laboratory is working purpose , equipment , work to go table in fillings can Together work order

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discussion so how to the results their achievements about as comments are also possible .

Virtual laboratories after reason :

- Motivation gain
- Education quality about ;
- Lesson work interesting so organize reach
- Equipment lack of cultivation person ;
- To the teacher from time fruitful send by to give
- Technique about from time according to more provide grow up person ;
- Har one laboratory from training before this install , re collection , action based on their to the place to put for time spending absence ;
 - Various in the circumstances short time inside one several experiences transfer , then the results generalization and about release by to give
 - Simple in the circumstances impossible has been the experience transfer by give (eg process long continuous if or special installations demand if he does).
 - laboratory their work about through students to real processes preparation , use the experience repetition and mistakes man
 - remote education union about ;

From this additional , virtual laboratory work some topics do it sent to the student spaces to fill by , student task education in the part or movement at home can Laboratory of work this type to the student independent learning by .

Conclusion .

Study processing success his scientific to the character have to be , worker and systematic learning , demonstration , education conscious and activity of students independent education such as about to events comply with to be taken depend Knowledge conscious and active appropriation national is being studied materialization to the content , perhaps study processing to himself has been it also depends on work . Independent work in the process and experience in transfer consciousness and activity develops .

virtual laboratories lesson in the process send demand to science was things about level about service does and of students independent works with together , naturally natural sciences according to knowledge , maybe interesting and modern

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technologies , computers with work taking over the defense as well by .Students known one lesson topic with not limited beam research activity with engage in and data themselves analysis to do to learn have will be In class of students production organize education process individualization of the lesson control to do possible will be

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